

Burnout and grit of selected senior high school students in Bacoor, Cavite: Basis in the development of positive psychological intervention program

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Abstract

Students in the Senior High School have encountered varied difficulties from academic burdens to their extra-curricular activities comprising the academic package of school works which leads them to experience burnout; as for students who are showing passion and sustained persistence for a long-term goal has a low burnout level (Cavanaugh, 2018) and able to finish school deadlines. Through a research-made 5-point Likert scale of burnout and grit, data were gathered from the three schools in Bacoor City, Cavite with 120 respondents. However, due to the unexpected COVID-19 pandemic, the data gathering was done online which dropped the number of respondents to thirty-one (31) using convenient sampling. For the mean score of Grit, male respondents have 3.41 with a verbal interpretation of Average Grit, while for the female respondents have 3.30 with a verbal interpretation of Average Grit. For the mean score of Burnout, male respondents have 3.05 with a verbal interpretation of Average Burnout and for female respondents have 2.97 with a verbal interpretation of Average Burnout. For the significant difference, the computed Grit p-value is 0.34 and for Burnout p-value is 0.68, that the null hypothesis is accepted. The correlation between Grit and Burnout with regards to Pearson's r value is 0.419 which is a low positive correlation. Therefore, when Grit increases, Burnout decreases. This research could lead into high positive correlation if the number of respondents is until four hundred (400).

Keywords: Grit; Burnout; High school students.

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Introduction

In the educational system, high school life is the period that influences the future of a person and to navigate the fields that a person may want to take. Area selection establishes and restrictions of higher education programs which can be studied. In this case, commitment of an adolescent may be very well prepared in forthcoming examinations and to get high remarks, short-term purpose may be to keep this success in the student's classes and build up performances in academic work. Long-term purpose is to work in a decent profession, to go abroad, to build an academic vocation, to construct and generate important invention, etc. In this process, students are entailed to select important pronouncements and to be in an unremitting struggle. All these stages are faced together with difficulties of adolescent life of students (Smetana et al., 2006).

Students experience stress since some are trying to cope with the demands of adapting to a new living environment, new peers, academic pressure. These situations can leave them with

trembling hands, tense muscles, migraine, headache, and multiple other symptoms of stress performance or reduce the student to ineffectiveness. Generally, all students, regardless of their academic classification pointed out that academics, workload due to subjects, and time management were their main stressors. They all reacted to stress with affective stress responses. These patterns can be monitored to maintain the psychological and physical well-being of adolescent students. It is necessary to research because today the government changed the curriculum and students have difficulty to come up to this kind of event (Bonnie et al., 2015).

Adolescence is one of the most critical and difficult periods in human life, which is between childhood and adulthood, physically, sexually, cognitively, morally, socially, and emotionally developing of an individual, facing rapid changes in the body. Transition of intimate relations of family environment to intimate relations of circle of friends; inclination to individuality and independence; search for identity; acclimatizing to social and sexual roles; identification efforts to discover the ideal ego; attempt to make and search for a distinct, varied and something new; acknowledgement and adoption of body image and living content with it which can be considered amid the most focal developmental stresses compelling the adolescents and which must be undergone by the essence of this period. A young individual has trouble in both emotionally, cognitively, and social levels where the stress and anxiety require new adaptations.

Excessive amount of work, poor standard, and quality of resting time, students' demands cannot be met, deficiency of professional expertise of administrators and teachers, short supply of supervision activities, incompatibility among students, lack of social environments, demands of administrator and teacher, and non-democratic classroom management that cause stress at school for students. Socio-economic status of family discords out of school, parent education, living environment of family, usage of cigarette and alcohol are amongst the causes of stress outside the school for adolescent students (Oghuvbu, 2007). Stress occurs when there is disparity between capacities of individual and needs of the environment. Humans undergo amidst an alarmed state to protect itself against stress, subsequently it offers resistance and finally stress that results into exhaustion and fatigue that reaches serious levels which develops into burnout. Burnout is acclaimed as an outcome of failed endeavors to cope with an assortment of negative stressful situations.

Research reports on burnout have accordingly called for action to improve approaches to avert and lighten the patterns of stress and anxieties in burnout. Notwithstanding both disputed and fervent appeals for action, development has been diffident. The progress that has been cropped up delivers a concrete basis for forthcoming work, but much remains to be achieved. Recently, positive psychology has arisen as an innovative way to impart individuals to cope more efficiently with stress and burnout (Grossman et al., 2004). The purpose in this study was to test the feasibility and efficiency of a specialized development program for students aimed at the diminution of academic stress and indicators of burnout through mindfulness training (MT) by correlating first if low mindfulness is associated to high burnout. The MT program under investigation aims to assist students in developing skills and mind-sets that are conjectured to manage to stress reduction, resilience enhancement, and the improvement of learning in the schools as well as the quality of life of the students (Davidson et al., 2012; Roeser et al., 2012). Through mindfulness training, for instance, individuals are trained how to examine their internal responses to fervently reduce circumstances and thus know when they are in the grasps of a sentiment and need to take time to soothe down before retorting. In addition, individuals who took part MT are taught how to

nurture an attitude of compassion and empathy toward themselves, particularly during instants of inconvenience that inexorably ascend on the job and in life more in general.

Methods

This study utilized the descriptive-quantitative type of research. This research answers the strength and level of correlation between Grit and Burnout among senior high school students. The procedure on selecting respondents for this research was by random selection in five different senior high schools in Bacoor City. The researchers have selected three different senior high school classes around Bacoor City, Cavite. In every selected class there were 40 randomly selected students. The study developed a 5-point 15-item Likert-Scale for Burnout and Grit. The developed test or survey form was subjected to face and content validity. Researchers identified subject matter experts to check the fitness of each item per test or survey by scoring each item objectively. With the aid of statistics, coefficient alpha was calculated to establish good reliability score.

The researchers developed a 5-point 15-item Likert Scale survey form for burnout and grit. After valid and reliable items are identified, a final self-made test will be administered to the respondents. The researchers made a letter to the heads of senior high schools in Bacoor City, Cavite for the participation of the students in the study. Once approval is obtained from the heads of the senior high schools in Bacoor City, Cavite, a schedule for survey was set, however during the data gathering, the COVID-19 pandemic has occurred which forced the researchers to gather data using social media accounts. The total number of 120 target respondents was not reached. So, only 32 students responded. After the survey, the forms will be collected, tallied, and run-in statistical analysis.

Results and Analysis

Table 1. Mean Score for Grit

Gender	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Description
Male	3.41	Sometimes	Average Grit
Female	3.30	Sometimes	Average Grit
Average	3.34	Sometimes	Average Grit

Table 1 presents the mean score for Grit. For male respondents, the mean score is 3.41 with a verbal interpretation of sometimes and description of Average Grit. For female respondents, the mean score is 3.30 with a verbal interpretation of sometimes and a description of Average Grit.

Table 2. Mean Score for Burnout

Gender	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Description
Male	3.05	Sometimes	Average Burnout
Female	2.97	Sometimes	Average Burnout
Average	3.00	Sometimes	Average Burnout

Table 2 illustrates the mean score for Burnout. For male respondents, the mean score is 3.06 with a verbal interpretation of sometimes and description of Average Burnout. For female respondents, the mean score is 2.97 with a verbal interpretation of sometimes description of Average Burnout.

Table 3. Test for Significant Difference

Factor	p-value	Significance	H₀ Decision
Grit	0.34	Not Significant	Accept
Burnout	0.68	Not Significant	Accept

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

Table 3 reveals the test for significant difference for burnout and grit. For Grit, the computed p-value is 0.34 which is less than .05 alpha level. This would mean that difference is not significant and null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between mean scores of male and female grit. They perceived the same level of grit at an average level.

For Burnout, the computed p-value is 0.68 which is higher than .05 alpha level. This would mean that difference is not significant and null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between mean scores of male and female grit. They perceived the same level of burnout at an average level.

Table 4. Test for Correlation

Pearson's r value	Level of Correlation	p-value	Significance	H₀ Decision
0.419	Low Positive Correlation	0.02	Significant	Reject

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

Table 4 evidences the test for correlation between grit and burnout. The computed Pearson's r value is 0.419 which is low positive correlation. However, the computed p-value is 0.02 is lower than .05 alpha level. This would mean the correlation is significant and we reject null hypothesis.

Discussion

It is supported by the existing research that grit variations show with age and it is likely that it cannot be used as basis among younger students because their interests are not stable yet and constant efforts have not made it apparent. Novelty seeking behavior can be considered adaptive among young adults who are not yet ready to discover what they are good at (Duckworth et al., 2007). Therefore, both genders show that grit is more evident among older population.

This finding is supported by a previous research that stress affects time management and efficiency in studying. A regular schedule in studying is important in reducing academic pressure and helps fulfill their goals (Khan et al., 2013). According to Watson (2002), similar results found in the non-significant difference with reference to stress between male and female students. Adapting to coping time management and efficient strategies has shown great results in study habits toward gender differences.

From the study conducted by Bazalais et al. (2016), results have failed to reveal a significant difference between male and female genders. Gender differences have been observed with specific population among male and female levels of grit. It is stated from Meriac (2015) that work ethics is stable differences among cultural groups and gender. Furthermore, Rojas et al. (2012) found that females reported have higher grit than males. In their study, Jaeger et al. (2010) found that female students were grittier than their male counterparts.

From the study of Backovic et al. (2012), male and female students presented no significant difference between genders. Wherein, academic stress influence and mental health status in the first generation of students enrolled. According to Velasco (2019), Filipino millennials in the university seem not to be experiencing burnout. In contrast, from claimed studies of Misra and McKean (2000) and Galbraith and Merrill (2012), female university students tend to have higher academic burnout.

In a study of Cavanaugh (2018) it shows that students have significant, positive correlation between burnout and grit. When grit increases, students reduced sense of accomplishment, physical, and emotional exhaustion. This would mean that as grit increases, burnout decreases.

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